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Executive Summary

The EERIE (European Eddy-Rich Earth system models) project addresses the long-standing under-representation of ocean mesoscale eddies in climate models by delivering eddy-rich coupled simulations. This report presents a first cross-evaluation of ocean eddy characteristics in EERIE simulations, focusing on how increased resolution improves the representation of eddy population, structure, and energetics. The high-resolution models (grid spacing <math><10\text{ km}</math>) employed in EERIE capture 82–88% of the observed eddies, a major improvement over the ~55% achieved by medium-resolution (~25 km) configurations. These findings, consistent with Moreton et al. (2020) and other studies, confirm that transitioning from eddy-permitting to eddy-resolving regimes substantially enhances model fidelity across diverse model architectures. Despite global improvements, regional biases remain. High-resolution models better capture the frequent occurrence of eddies in western boundary currents, but still underestimate eddy kinetic energy there. These models also show reduced eddy occurrence in eastern boundary regions, presumably related to still insufficient resolution to fully capture the eddy formation processes in these regions. In the Southern Ocean, eddy biases are closely linked to mean circulation biases, highlighting the importance of the accurate modeling of the large-scale circulation. In polar regions, models reproduce expected seasonal and under-ice eddy modulations, although observational limitations hinder full validation. Overall, the high-resolution EERIE models reliably represent fundamental mesoscale ocean dynamics, laying a strong foundation for future studies of climate variability and change.

1 Introduction

Ocean mesoscale eddies – coherent rotating structures with horizontal scales of 10–100 km – constitute the oceanic equivalent of atmospheric weather systems and account for approximately 80% of the ocean kinetic energy budget (Ferrari & Wunsch 2009; Chelton et al. 2011). Eddies influence global circulation patterns, marine ecosystems dynamics, and climate regulation through their role in the oceanic uptake and redistribution of heat and carbon (Hallberg & Gnanadesikan 2006; Busecke & Abernathy 2019; Griffies et al. 2015; Llorc et al. 2018). In the recent decade, global Earth System Models have progressed from non-eddy-permitting regimes ($>1^\circ$ horizontal resolution) in the ocean to eddy-permitting (0.25°) configurations, yet this resolution remains insufficient to fully resolve mesoscale dynamics across all latitudes. Therefore, a major goal of the EERIE project is to understand the climatically-relevant up-scale effects of explicitly resolving these mesoscale features within high-resolution global coupled models.

The High Resolution Model Intercomparison Project (HighResMIP) demonstrated substantial improvements when transitioning from 1° to 0.25° ocean resolution; however, substantial biases still persist in the 0.25° resolution models (Moreno-Chamarro et al. 2022). The theoretical framework established by Hallberg (2013) suggests that a true eddy-resolving ocean model requires grid spacing ≥ 2 times finer than the first baroclinic Rossby radius of deformation (LR), which varies latitudinally from ~ 200 km at the equator to <10 km in polar regions. Consequently, nominally high-resolution models (0.25°) remain effectively laminar in high latitudes where LR decreases substantially, implying that mesoscale processes remain unresolved. In addition to the resulting shortfall in the simulated mesoscale kinetic energy in these models (Storer et al. 2022), these models also have more 40% fewer eddies than the observations suggest (Moreton et al. 2020). This improved when the resolution of the ocean models was increased to $1/12^\circ$, but even at this resolution, Moreton et al. (2020) diagnosed a 37% shortfall in the number of simulated eddies. By running a larger-suite of fully coupled ocean-atmosphere-sea-ice models at oceanic resolutions ranging from $\sim 1/12^\circ$ to as fine as $1/20^\circ$ (5 km), the EERIE project aims to assess whether the fidelity of these models with regard to the simulation of the oceanic mesoscale has improved further.

Simulating the oceanic mesoscale with high fidelity has proven critical for accurately representing a large number of critical processes in the ocean. This include (i) global ocean stratification & circulation (Marshall & Radko 2003, Roberts et al. 2020) (ii) the lateral transport and air-sea fluxes of momentum, freshwater, heat & other tracers (Nagai et al., 2015, Lovecchio et al., 2018); the rate of carbon sequestration (Bourgeois et al., 2016); and climate sensitivity (Chassignet et al. 2020, Hewitt et al. 2020, and references therein).

A key driver of mesoscale-derived climate sensitivity is eddy saturation, whereby the Antarctic Circumpolar Current transport remains relatively insensitive to wind stress changes

(Straub 1993 and Boning, et al. 2008). Munday et al. (2013) first quantified the sensitivity of eddy saturation on model resolution, demonstrating that while coarse-resolution models exhibit a 30–40% increase in ACC transport with doubled wind stress, eddy-permitting models show only a 2–10% increase. Still, the extent to which the eddy field and moderating transport responds to changes in atmospheric forcing is uncertain (Kong et al. 2021; Zhang et al. 2021), in part due to the short satellite record (Hogg et al. 2022). Nonetheless, the eddy saturation process fundamentally influences our understanding of how the Southern Ocean responds to changing wind patterns, with implications for carbon uptake and heat storage in a changing climate (Munday et al. 2014; Dietze et al. 2017).

The complex interplay between sea ice and mesoscale eddies is another aspect requiring high resolution. Sea ice modulates eddy formation through its impact on ocean-atmosphere momentum & heat fluxes, while eddies influence sea ice distribution through heat transport and mechanical forcing (Horvat et al. 2016, Manucharyan & Thompson 2022). Sea ice in turn also mechanically dampens the eddy kinetic energy, featuring strong seasonal variability. Current eddy-permitting models cannot adequately resolve these ice-ocean boundary processes, leading to systematic biases in simulated sea ice extent and distribution.

Utilising global coupled climate simulations at unprecedented resolution, the EERIE project is addressing critical gaps in our understanding of mesoscale eddy dynamics and their role in the Earth system. By explicitly resolving more of these processes, we aim to enhance model fidelity and improve predictions of climate variability across multiple temporal and spatial scales. To this end, we present here a first evaluation and intercomparison of global eddy statistics within the control simulations of the 4 eddy-resolving EERIE models. In this report, we have utilised, complemented, and extended many of the results provided in EERIE deliverable D6.1 “Assessing the mean state of the models” (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14802628>) (Delpech et al. 2024).

The report is organised to systematically evaluate the mesoscale eddy representation across the EERIE models. Section 2 details the models, observational datasets, and methodologies used in the analysis. Section 3 focuses on the global eddy characteristics, starting in S3.1 with an Eulerian view (eddy kinetic energy), before delving into tracked Lagrangian eddy statistics and properties in the latter subsections. Section 4 focuses specifically on mesoscale eddy-sea ice interactions in polar regions, exploring seasonal variations in both Arctic and Antarctic domains. Finally, Section 5 synthesises these findings on resolution-dependent model fidelity and discusses persistent regional biases in eddy representation.

2 Models and Methods

2.1 EERIE models

This deliverable is based on model simulation results from three modeling systems (MPI-ICON, AWI-IFS-FESOM, MetO-HadGEM3) in four configurations (3 eddy-resolving and one non-eddy resolving). The characteristics of these 4 model configurations are listed in Tables 1-3. The reader interested in more details is referred to the tables in Deliverable D6.1, on which tables 1-3 are based. Also listed in the tables are the characteristics of BSC-IFS-NEMO, although data from this model are not used in this report. This is because the control run was not available at the time of the analysis.

Two of the ocean models employ an unstructured grid (MPI-ICON and AWI-IFS-FESOM), while the two configurations of MetO-HadGEM3 are based on a structured tripolar grid. With a nominal ocean resolution of ~5 km, the MPI-ICON configuration has the highest resolution, while the resolution of the ocean eddy-resolving MetO-HadGEM3 configuration (henceforth HadGEM3-HH) has a resolution of 1/12°, which is equivalent to 9.2 km at the equator and 4.6 km at 60° latitude. In contrast, the eddy permitting configuration of MetO-HadGEM3 (henceforth HadGEM3-MM) has a resolution of 1/4°. We will use this mid-resolution version to highlight the advances made when switching from eddy permitting to eddy-resolving resolutions. But we also note that a direct comparison of the model resolution across the different grid types employed by the different models is not straightforward, as the relationship between resolution and grid structure differs significantly between triangular and quadrilateral meshes (see Danilov 2022). In addition, the resolution of the atmospheric components of these coupled models differ: ICON and IFS-FESOM use an atmosphere with a nominal resolution of 9 km, while HadGEM3-HH and HadGEM3-MM have an average resolution of about 21km. This allows HadGEM3-HH and HadGEM3-MM to have longer model runs (Figure 1).

Model name	ICON	IFS-FESOM	HadGEM3-GC5-EERIE	HadGEM3-GC5-EERIE	IFS-NEMO
Ocean code version	ICON-O v2.6.6	FESOM 2.5	NEMO v4.0.4	NEMO v4.0.4	NEMO v4.0.7
Horizontal resolution	Unstructured icosahedral grid. 5 km resolution globally.	Unstructured grid, ~13 km at the equator, ~5.5 km at 60°	Tripolar grid, 1/12°. 9.2 km at the equator 4.6 km at 60°	Tripolar grid, 1/4°	Tripolar grid, 1/12°. 9.2 km at the equator 4.6 km at 60°
Number of vertical levels	72	70	75	75	75

Thickness of the top model layer	2 m	5 m	1 m	1m	1 m
Vertical coordinate	z*	z*	z*	z*	z*

Table 1: General characteristics of EERIE models

Model name	ICON	IFS-FESOM	HadGEM3-GC5-EERIE	HadGEM3-GC5-EERIE	IFS-NEMO
Lateral advection of momentum	Vector invariant form (Korn 2018)	Scalar	Vector form, 2nd order enstrophy and energy conserving	Vector form, 2nd order enstrophy and energy conserving	Vector form - 2nd order centered scheme
Gent-McWilliams parameterization (GM)	No	Yes, according to Ferrari et al. 2010 resolution dependent	GM with coefficient that varies spatially and with model resolution	GM with coefficient that varies spatially and with model resolution	No
Fox-Kemper parameterization	None	None	None	None	None
Lateral mixing of momentum	biharmonic	biharmonic	biharmonic	biharmonic	biharmonic

Table 2: Ocean advection schemes and parameterization in EERIE models

Model name	ICON	IFS-FESOM	HadGEM3-GC5-EERIE	HadGEM3-GC5-EERIE	IFS-NEMO
Sea ice model	FESIM	FESIM	SI ³	SI ³	SI ³
Dynamics	FESIM EVP, interpolation from B-grid to C-grid	FESIM EVP, on A-grid	EVP rheology scheme	EVP rheology scheme	EVP rheology scheme
Thermodynamics	From MPI-OM	IFS thermodynamics	SI ³ (Blockley et al 2024)	SI ³ (Blockley et al 2024)	SI ³
Ice categories for dynamics	1	1	5	5	5
Ice categories for thermodynamics	1 ice, 1 snow	1 ice, 1 snow	4 layers of ice, 1 snow	4 layers of ice, 1 snow	4 layers of ice, 1 snow
Iceberg representation	None	None	Freshwater iceberg climatology	Freshwater iceberg climatology	None

Table 3: General characteristics of sea ice models and interactions with land ice

2.2 Data used in this report

2.2.1 Model data

For the analysis, mesoscale eddies are identified with py-eddy-tracker (see methods and Mason et al. 2014) on 20 years (19 years from HADGEM3 MM) of regridded 0.25 degree daily sea surface height (SSH) fields. We use the substantially coarsened data for our analyses for three reasons: First, this is also the resolution that the observational product is available for. Second, tests have shown that for the majority of eddy characteristics, using lower resolution data does not deteriorate the results substantially. Third, given the need for daily data, working with coarser resolution data in space reduces the computational and storage demands drastically. However, note that using a coarsened data introduces an uncertainty as eddies smaller than the grid-scale are not identified, even if they are resolved on the native grid. The effect of the regridded data resolution is planned to be explored in the future.

The following data sets are used:

- ICON EERIE cycle 2 control 1950 (1991-2011), in figures referred to as ICON
- IFS-FESOM EERIE control 1950 (1950-1970), in figures referred to as IFS-FESOM
- HadGEM3-GC5-EERIE control 1850 (1850-1870), in figures referred to as HADGEM3 HH
- Medium-resolution HadGEM3-GC5-EERIE control 1850 (1950-1970), in figures referred to as HADGEM3 MM

Figure 1. A schematic depiction of EERIE project model spin-up and control run length. Dashed areas indicate the years used for eddy analysis.

2.2.2 Observational data

To compare our findings to observations, we use primarily the altimetric Mesoscale Eddy Trajectories Atlas (META3.2) produced by SSALTO/DUACS and distributed by AVISO+ with support from CNES, in collaboration with IMEDEA (DOI: 10.24400/527896/a01-2022.005.220209). In this data product, ocean eddies were identified from interpolated satellite altimetry absolute dynamic topography (ADT) fields with the same package as used for the models (py-eddy-tracker). Identifying eddies on satellite altimetry ADT is directly comparable to using model SSH. Here, 20 years (1993-2013) of AVISO data set is used with daily eddy resolution. We acknowledge that eddies of different time periods (preindustrial control, 1950 control and observations from recent decades) are compared. However, we don't expect this mismatch of analysed time periods to be a large contributor to the differences between datasets. For comparing the summer and winter sea ice cover in the EERIE models against observations, we use sea ice concentration from OSI SAF (OSI-450-a; EUMETSAT Ocean and Sea Ice Satellite Application Facility, 2015).

While the AVISO dataset is the most widely used eddy observation dataset in scientific studies, it is not a perfect observation of the real ocean and it is useful to know about the caveats. Importantly, the gridded ADT field is generated through optimal interpolation from the merging of the tracks of multiple satellites. Even if the individual measurements were perfect, the merging and the required spatial and temporal interpolation introduces biases. For example, Amores et al. (2018) highlighted the issue that the spatial resolution of the gridded altimetry product is not enough to capture the small eddies that are the most abundant in the high-resolution simulations used as "ground truth" in the study. According to this analysis, only 16% of the total number of eddies in the Mediterranean Sea were detected with the AVISO/CMEMS products. The unresolved structures are aliased into larger structures or multiple small scale eddies are considered as one large eddy and therefore the gridded altimetry products contain a higher number of artificially large mesoscale eddies. Stegner et al. (2021) focuses on the asymmetry between cyclonic and anticyclonic eddy characteristics in AVISO dataset. We refer the reader to Amores et al. (2018) and Stegner et al. (2021) to a more in depth discussion of the AVISO biases.

Given that Amores et al. (2018) have shown that AVISO will miss eddies, largely because of their small size, we can conclude that it is likely that an eddy is missed multiple days in a row leading to eddy track discontinuity and the algorithm considering a long lived eddy as multiple shorter ones (illustrated in Figure 2). Additional drawback of AVISO observations is the lack of information about eddies under sea ice.

AVISO products are recommended only for the low and mid latitudes extending from 66°S to 66°N, since poleward of these latitudes, the data set relies on data from only one satellite. Furthermore the product has larger uncertainties closer to land, shallow water areas, and in sea ice covered regions (University of Hamburg, n.d.). Due to the limited observations for eddies under sea

ice, we do not have datasets based on observations for direct comparison covering both poles of wide spatio-temporal coverage to robustly describe eddy characteristics. A key exception is the sea level anomaly product created by Auger et al (2021), using data from three satellites for a period of seven years. Since there is no counterpart for Arctic Ocean to the best of our knowledge, we compare the properties of eddies under sea ice from the EERIE models against those from AVISO and OSI-SAF sea ice concentration, such that the data is the same for both polar regions, and this section is consistent with the rest of the eddy statistic evaluation in this report.

Model = one eddy (20 days)

Observations = two eddies (10 and 5 days)

Figure 2. An illustration of an example of how AVISO observations can introduce biases. Due to interpolation between satellite altimeter swaths to full ADT fields, it is likely that AVISO creates multiple short-lived eddies from a single long-lived eddy. Circles symbolise daily eddy instances and colored lines are eddy tracks.

2.3 Methods

2.3.1 Eddy identification and tracking

The py-eddy-tracker (Mason et al. 2014) method used here to identify mesoscale eddies in this report is an Eulerian eddy detection method that uses instantaneous information of the flow field. Due to the fact that eddies are transient features, they are detected in the anomaly fields. The basic concept of the Eulerian eddy detection method is to identify closed anomaly contours on the instantaneous flow field for multiple time steps. The tracking is done by connecting the anomaly

contours in neighbouring time steps by estimating how far the contours could have moved between the snapshots. The fields that have been used to identify eddy closed contours include Okubo-Weiss parameter (Isern-Fontanet et al. 2004), sea surface height (SSH) (Chelton et al. 2011), velocity streamlines (Nencioli et al 2010), sea surface temperature (Dong et al. 2011) and potential vorticity (Zhang et al. 2014). Here, the SSH fields are used to detect Eulerian eddies because this method is most comparable to how eddies are detected in AVISO observations. In this report “identified eddy” or “eddy instances” are used as well as “tracked eddies”. The former are individual eddy instances identified on one day. “Tracked eddy” refers to eddy instances being connected in neighbouring time steps to follow it through its lifetime.

There are drawbacks to consider when using the Eulerian method. For example, it is problematic to calculate coherent eddy transport due to the fact that Eulerian eddies cannot keep material coherence during their lifespan (Liu et al. 2022). That is, the Eulerian eddy boundaries are not material and these boundaries allow for water to be exchanged across them. As a result one would tend to overestimate their ability for material conservation and transport (Abernathey and Haller 2018). However, in this report, an assessment of surface eddy properties is carried out here, instead of a quantification of eddy transport, so Eulerian eddies serve the purpose.

The identification of eddies in this study is performed using the Python package `py-eddy-tracker` (Mason et al. 2014), which is also employed by the AVISO META3.2 data set we use for the evaluation of our model simulations. Additionally, it is very comparable to the eddy detection used in Moreton et al. (2020). This study offers a useful point of comparison for this report, as it explored the differences in eddy characteristics between an eddy permitting and an eddy-rich model. The eddy detection and tracking scheme includes adjustable parameters, and the values selected in this study are listed in Table 4. These parameters are identical to those used in AVISO META3.2, except for the amplitude threshold. However, variations in the amplitude threshold do not introduce significant changes in the resulting eddy dataset.

Filter	Lanczos filter with a Bessel window 2D (cutoff 700 km, order 1)
Maxima in one eddy	one
Shape error	70%
Amplitude threshold	0.4 cm in AVISO and 0.2 cm in all models
Minimum lifetime	10 days
Max days “missed” eddy observations that are substituted with virtual eddies	4 days

Table 4: Eddy identification and tracking parameter values

We focus here on the total eddy population, that is, we present results from both eddy polarities (cyclonic and anticyclonic) combined. This is because, in the first order, there are only limited differences between cyclonic and anticyclonic eddies. Only in specific sections, where a distinction is warranted, do we separate the population into its two polarities.

2.3.2 Eddy kinetic energy

Geostrophic eddy kinetic energy (GS EKE) quantifies the energy contained in mesoscale variability of ocean currents and serves as a fundamental diagnostic for evaluating ocean model fidelity. This metric captures the energy associated with transient oceanic features, such as coherent eddies. But the GS EKE fields also contains the energetic contribution of other mesoscale features, such as meanders, filaments, jets, or incoherent vortices that do not have a closed contour. By measuring the spatiotemporal variability of geostrophic motions, the GS EKE provides insight into a model's ability to resolve mesoscale dynamics, which are responsible for a significant fraction of oceanic energy transport and mixing.

The GS EKE field is computed directly from sea surface height (SSH) anomalies. We first construct a daily climatological SSH field, averaging across all analysis years. We then apply a 30-day rolling mean to this climatology to create a smoothed reference state and subtract it from the original SSH fields to isolate the transient mesoscale signal. The horizontal geostrophic velocity components, u_g and v_g , are subsequently derived from these SSH anomalies assuming geostrophic balance:

$$u_g = -\frac{g}{f} \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial y}; v_g = \frac{g}{f} \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial x}$$

where g is gravitational acceleration, f is the Coriolis parameter, and η represents the SSH anomaly. The gradients are computed using second-order centred differences on the 0.25-degree regridded data. The GS EKE is finally computed using these geostrophic velocity anomalies.

This calculation is applied uniformly across all datasets—including each EERIE model and the AVISO observational dataset—ensuring consistent intercomparison. By computing these nonlinear operations on the 0.25-degree regridded data, we in effect filter out and miss the small-scale energetic fluctuations. Despite this limitation, the standardised regridding across all EERIE & AVISO datasets permits a fair intercomparison. It is important to note that the above methodology differs from the pre-computed supplementary AVISO GS EKE product (not used in the presented work), which defines anomalies relative to a fixed long-term mean (1993–2012). By removing a smoothed daily climatology instead, our approach more effectively excludes seasonal variations (for example in the boundary current strength or location) thereby better isolating the mesoscale eddy signal.

2.4 Regions

To highlight and more closely examine regional differences, we average and present the statistics also for 4 distinct regions:

1. Eastern boundary currents (red) (ocean area covered $381 \times 10^5 \text{ km}^2$)
2. Western boundary currents (blue) (ocean area covered $361 \times 10^5 \text{ km}^2$)
3. North Atlantic (orange) (ocean area covered $638 \times 10^4 \text{ km}^2$)
4. Equatorial (green) (ocean area covered $103 \times 10^6 \text{ km}^2$)
5. Southern Ocean (purple) (ocean area covered $444 \times 10^5 \text{ km}^2$)

The five study regions were chosen to represent diverse oceanic environments covering over 60% of global ocean surface. Western boundary currents (e.g., Gulf Stream, Kuroshio) were selected as high-energy environments characterized by intense eddy kinetic energy (EKE) and strong mean flows (Chelton et al. 2011), while eastern boundary currents (e.g., California Current, Benguela Current) provide contrasting low-EKE systems with moderate eddy activity (Chaigneau et al., 2009). The North Atlantic was included for its frequent eddy formation despite the lack of strong associated currents and with likely implications for water mass transformation. The equatorial region exhibits distinctive large, but unstable, (short-lived) eddies due to the minimal Coriolis effect near the equator (Chelton et al., 2011). The Southern Ocean band (45° - 55° S) represents an area of strong mean currents and high shear. We limit the southern boundary to 55° S, in order to avoid zones that occasionally include sea-ice, as this prevents satellite altimetry observations, introducing potential biases.

In addition to these five regions, we discuss in detail the polar oceans in both hemispheres in section 4. This is justified by the specific characteristics of under ice eddies and the difficulties in observing them.

Figure 3. A map of ocean regions used in this report. The regions are divided based on possible regional eddy characteristics. Red - Eastern boundary current systems, blue - Western boundary current systems, green - equatorial region, purple - Southern Ocean (without sea ice), orange - North Atlantic.

3 Global eddy characteristics

3.1 Eddy kinetic energy

Figure 4. Maps of geostrophic eddy kinetic energy (GS EKE) and the differences between datasets. Left column are EKE fields for (a) ICON, (c) IFS-FESOM, (e) HADGEM3 MM, (g) HADGEM3 HH, (i) AVISO. EKE is calculated as the anomaly from a 30-day rolling mean of the daily climatology of sea surface height (SSH); cf. S2.3.2. The right side column shows the corresponding difference relative to the AVISO observations. Panel (j) shows the difference between the HADGEM3 HH & MM runs.

Figure 5. Maps of barotropic streamfunction. The 20-year mean of the depth-averaged streamfunction for the same experiments corresponding to the EKE plots, and observational reanalysis provided by ECCOV4 (e). Isolines are spaced by 20 Sv. Volume transports are shown for notable major current systems measured in the same location across models independent of spatial variability. Both the Gulf Stream measurement location (corresponding to Rossby et al. (2014)) and the Kuroshio (on the ASUKA line) are intended to not include the recirculation.

Figure 6. Mean EKE globally and by region in all datasets. 4 different ocean regions (Eastern boundary currents, Western boundary currents, Southern Ocean, North Atlantic (see Figure 3)) and the global mean (excluding ± 5 degrees around equator) are used for all datasets. Equatorial region is omitted due to the Coriolis parameter going to zero. Data shown are averaged for 20 years of control run for the models, and from 1993 to 2013 for AVISO.

Before assessing the identified coherent mesoscale eddies, it is important to evaluate the geostrophic eddy kinetic energy (GS EKE) field, as coherent eddies constitute only a fraction of the total mesoscale energy budget, with this fraction varying significantly by region (Martinez-Moreno et al. 2019). The GS EKE distributions (Figure 4) in the high-resolution models capture the observed spatial patterns remarkably well, reproducing major energetic hotspots in Western Boundary Currents (WBCs) and the Antarctic Circumpolar Current (ACC) at comparable magnitudes. Low-energy regions are similarly well-represented, though model values consistently fall below observations. This discrepancy likely stems from measurement and interpolation uncertainties introducing background noise in the observational dataset (Amores et al. 2018). Quantitatively, mean global EKE in observations exceeds the high-resolution models by 24-38%, while the medium-resolution model captures only 45% of observed kinetic energy (Figure 6). Despite observational uncertainties complicating direct comparison, the visible improvement with increased resolution demonstrates that eddy-rich models better capture the energetics of the ocean mesoscale.

The barotropic streamfunction provides context for interpreting EKE disparities by revealing the underlying mean circulation contributing, in part, to the eddy generation. Positional biases in major current systems directly impact the eddy field, as is particularly evident in the Western Boundary Currents. For example, the Kuroshio in ICON separates from Japan too far north compared to observations (cf. EERIE deliverable D6.1), manifesting as a clear north-south dipole (negative-positive) in the EKE bias field (Figure 4 (b)). While IFS-FESOM and HadGEM3-HH capture the Kuroshio separation latitude more accurately, all models struggle with the Gulf Stream path, exhibiting more zonal elongation rather than the observed northeastward orientation after Cape Hatteras. These positional biases in the major current systems have a direct impact on GS EKE biases (right column of Figure 4). For an in-depth discussion on the location & strength of the mean currents in EERIE models, we refer the reader to D6.1 chapter 3. Overall, this WBC regional analysis highlights the difficulty models have in reproducing these sensitive current systems, ultimately resulting in even the high-resolution models capturing only approximately 60% of observed Western Boundary Current EKE, and declining to 40% in the medium-resolution simulation. Furthermore, these biases in the eddy activity within WBCs can feed back on the eddy-driven inertial recirculation.

The Southern Ocean regional analysis also reveals a pattern with biases in the mean flow strength and mesoscale energetics. It is known that the intra-model relationship between EKE and ACC strength is rather decoupled, owing to the eddy compensation mechanism whereby changes in eddy activity can partially offset variations in mean flow strength (Bishop et al., 2016). However, inter-model variations in the ACC strength may still be related to (or causing) variations in the Southern Ocean EKE. Indeed, here we find a 25% weaker volume transport through the Drake Passage in IFS-FESOM (Figure 5) is coincident with a 25% less energetic Southern Ocean (Figure 4) – in both cases relative to the high-resolution models and observations. Still, contemporary measurements indicate a Drake Passage transport of approximately 170 Sv (Donohue et al., 2016), significantly exceeding modelled values (111-135 Sv).

These identified biases in both circulation strength and eddy kinetic energy raise fundamental questions about coherent eddy representation—specifically, whether disparities in the mesoscale energetics translate to differences in the properties of identifiable mesoscale eddies. This will be explored in detail in the next sections.

3.2 Eddy number and lifetime

Figure 7. Illustrative maps of simulated eddy tracks and lifetime. The eddy tracks shown are full tracks of eddy instances that occurred on a randomly selected day in the (a) high resolution (HADGEM3 HH) and (b) mid-resolution (HADGEM3 MM) models and (c) AVISO observations. Eddy tracks are colored by their lifetime and the red dot marks eddy birthplace. The subselection of full tracks of a random day is done to improve readability while simultaneously displaying eddies with a wide range of lifetimes. Both cyclonic and anticyclonic eddies are shown but not distinguished.

Before quantifying eddy statistics, it is valuable to qualitatively assess eddy tracks in models. Figure 7 displays eddy tracks and the associated lifetimes based on simulation results from the medium- (HADGEM3 MM) and high- resolution (HADGEM3 HH) models and observations (AVISO). First, models seem to be able to produce eddies with lifetimes of the same order of magnitude as those in observations. Second, models capture the general westward eddy propagation, as well as the eastward propagating eddies in strong mean-current areas, like the Gulf Stream and the ACC (Chelton et al. 2011). In addition, there is a lack of eddy tracks in the medium-resolution model, when compared to the high-resolution model or observations (more discussion and occurrence density map in section 3.3 below). Especially noticeable is the lack of eddies (of all lifetimes) in the EBC systems, their propagation into the open ocean and generally lower number of eddies around 40-50 degrees.

Moreton et al. (2020) explored eddy representation in HADGEM3 HH and MM resolution models and found that eddy lifetime peaks around 20-50° in both hemispheres, which we can also observe in the track colors in Figure 7. It is expected that in the equatorial region the eddies are short-lived and don't travel large distances because of the break-down of geostrophy due to the very weak Coriolis force and eddies being more linear because the ratio of velocity to the Rossby wave speed is lower. The results show that in the medium resolution model there are eddies at high latitudes, even though the Rossby radius of deformation (R_d) is substantially smaller than the grid scale (discussed in detail in Moreton et al. (2020) and Tulloch et al. (2011)).

Figure 8. Number of eddy instances and tracked eddies, tracked eddy time series and lifetime distribution.

(a) The mean number of eddy instances per year that make up the tracked eddies. In (a) and (b) the light colored bar section is the number of long-lived eddies (lifetime >30 days), dark colored bar section for short-lived eddy (lifetime 10-30 days) number. (b) Mean number of tracked eddies per year, (c) 19-year time series of annual tracked eddy numbers. (d) The distribution of eddy lifetimes for all models and observations. In all plots both cyclonic and anticyclonic eddies are considered.

We start the quantitative assessment of the mesoscale eddies in the models by considering the overall number of identified eddies. Figure 8 shows the mean number of (a) eddy instances and (b) tracked eddies per year for each of the datasets. Only those eddy instances that comprise tracked eddies are considered. All of the eddy statistics are shown for the full eddy dataset (20 years for all datasets, except HADGEM3 MM, which has 19 years) and for eddy lifetimes longer than 10 days, unless specified otherwise.

Overall, the models reproduce the same number of eddies as observations, for both tracked and not-tracked eddies. For tracked eddies, the high-resolution models capture 82-88% of the observed eddies, while the medium-resolution model has only about 55% of the tracked eddy number. The higher-resolution models allow for a more realistic representation of the cumulative

number of eddies. Interestingly, ICON has about 10% more identified eddy instances than AVISO even if the tracked eddy number is lower. This is in agreement with D6.1 findings of ICON showing a higher background SSH standard deviation than other models.

Although cyclonic and anticyclonic eddies display only small differences in most properties and regions, an asymmetry exists in their lifetimes. However, this difference is seen only for very long-lived eddies. With all eddies considered (lifetime >10 days) then median lifetimes are similar for both polarities. However, when very long-lived eddies are considered (lifetime >1 year), the mean lifetime of anticyclones is higher than for cyclones (by 15 days), suggesting that anticyclones dominate very long-lived eddy numbers. Chelton et al., (2011) showed that eddies with large amplitude or spatial scale tend to persist longer than smaller, weaker eddies and that eddies with the longest lifetimes and largest propagation distances tend to be anticyclonic. Anticyclonic eddies are more robust against external strain and shear, maintaining their structure more effectively than cyclonic eddies (e.g. Stegner et al., 2022, Perret et al., 2011).

There is only a small (around 5%) variation of eddy number between years in all models (Figure 8 (c)). This shows that there is little interannual variability of eddy number in the model control runs.

In observations, the mean global eddy lifetime is 42 days, compared to a mean eddy lifetime of 53 days in all models. The histogram of eddy lifetimes (Figure 8 (d)) also shows that there are more short-lived and less long-lived eddies in the AVISO dataset than in any of the models. This difference in eddy lifetime between models and observations supports the idea that the AVISO-based data set could be biased and that it contains too many short-lived eddies simply because it failed to connect the tracks of a long-lived eddy, and thus suggests two short-lived eddies instead of a single long-lived eddy. This potential bias poses a challenge in validating the models. On the other hand, there is also the potential for the models to overestimate the lifetime. For example Moreton et al. (2020) suggested that high-resolution models might overestimate the survival-rate of eddies, because a variety of eddy dissipation mechanisms, like enhanced friction over rough bottom topography, the emission of internal waves, coupling to the atmosphere, the role of symmetric instability in the open ocean or interaction with WBCs (Zhai et al. 2010, Clément et al., 2016; Gula et al. 2016, Yu et al. 2019), are not captured in the models. Indeed, compared to high-resolution models, HADGEM3 MM has a lower number of eddies that have lifetimes between 10 days and up to 1 year but a comparable amount of eddies that are very long-lived and are tracked for more than a year, which supports the idea of a higher eddy survival rate.

Figure 9. A scatter plot of regional mean EKE plotted against the regional median eddy occurrence per year for all datasets. Mean EKE values are the same as Figure 6 and median eddy occurrence values are the median values from Figure 10 density distributions. Each region is shown in a different symbol and each dataset in a different color, according to the legends. The values are calculated for the whole analysis period for anticyclonic and cyclonic eddies with a lifetime of at least 10 days.

In Figure 9 neither models nor the observations show a clear relationship between EKE and the number of eddies, with the exception of the mid-resolution HADGEM3 model whose EKE and eddy number are clearly lower. The absence of a relationship between EKE and the number of eddies across regions indicates that different regions differ substantially in their fraction of mesoscale motions that occur within coherent eddies, i.e., these regions are dominated by filaments, meanders, and other features, all contributing to EKE, but not to the number of eddies. This effect might be particularly strong in the western boundary current regions, which have high EKE, but not more eddies than e.g., the eastern boundary current regions. Overall, all high-resolution models capture the rank in EKE, but not the rank in eddy number. Still, with regard to EKE and the number of eddies, the advantage of using high-resolution models over their coarser resolution configurations is very strong.

In summary, EERIE models generally capture EKE distributions well, but underestimate EKE in key

regions, particularly Western Boundary Currents (WBCs) and the Southern Ocean, likely due to weaker modeled mean flow. Eddy track assessments show that while the high-resolution models reproduce realistic eddy lifetimes and propagation patterns, there are still discrepancies, especially in Eastern Boundary Current (EBC) systems. A quantitative evaluation of eddy numbers finds that high-resolution models capture 82-88% of tracked eddies in observations, whereas medium-resolution models only capture 55%. However, models tend to overestimate eddy lifetimes, with an average of 53 days compared to 42 days in observations, potentially due to missing dissipation processes such as bottom friction, internal wave emission, and ocean-atmosphere coupling. But it also needs to be pointed out that eddy lifetime determined from observations is substantially underestimated due to interpolation problems with the satellite altimeter fields.

3.3 Occurrence frequency

Figure 10. Maps of the mean eddy occurrence instances per year. The mean number of annual cyclonic and anticyclonic eddy occurrence instances binned in 1 degree boxes for (a) IFS-FESOM, (b) ICON, (c) HADGEM3 HH, (d) HADGEM3 MM, (e) AVISO. The mean is calculated for the whole analysis period for eddies with a lifetime of at least 10 days.

Figure 11. Eddy occurrence zonal mean. Zonal mean of the annual number of cyclonic and anticyclonic eddy occurrence instances in 1 degree latitudinal bands for all models and observations. The mean is calculated for the whole analysis period for eddies with a lifetime of at least 10 days.

Figure 12. Regional eddy occurrence distributions. Density distribution of the annual number of eddy occurrence instances for cyclonic and anticyclonic eddies in 5 different ocean regions ((a) Eastern boundary currents, (b) Western boundary currents, (c) Equator, (d) Southern Ocean, (e) North Atlantic, see Figure 3) for all models and observations. The whole analysis period for eddies with a lifetime of at least 10 days is considered.

The next step is to assess the distribution of the cumulative number of eddy instances throughout the entire ocean by assessing eddy occurrences binned in 1 degree boxes per year. Even if the cumulative eddy number is similar between models and observations, the differences are more prevalent when specific eddy characteristics and regions are examined.

The high-resolution models capture the general eddy distribution pattern in the global ocean seen in observations. The zonal averages (Figure 11) show excellent agreement, especially in the Northern hemisphere. The spread is larger in the Southern hemisphere, especially around 30°S to 50°S.

The largest difference exists between the medium-resolution HADGEM3 MM and the rest of the datasets. Figure 10 shows that the difference in eddy occurrence is the largest in the extratropics between 20-60°, with the MM model having as little as 50% of the high-resolution model eddy occurrences. This is mostly a direct consequence of the lower overall number of tracked eddies. Interestingly, eddy occurrences in the equatorial region (between 20°S and 20°N) the medium resolution model is able to capture eddy occurrences well, compared to observations and high-resolution models. The occurrence in the polar regions (poleward of 60°) is discussed in section 4.

In the Eastern Boundary current region the median eddy occurrence is 15% higher in observations than in high-resolution models. For example, in the California current system region, a belt of higher eddy observations can be seen around the continental margins, but further into the open ocean occurrence decreases, while that is less the case in observations. This is likely due to the lack of long-lived eddies in eastern boundary upwelling already mentioned in the quantitative eddy track assessment. Eastern boundary currents also are one of the main regions of stark difference between medium- and high-resolution models with HADGEM3 MM median occurrence being 35% smaller than the high-resolution models. The findings for all models align with Moreton et al. (2020), who concluded that while the high-resolution model significantly improves representation in eastern boundary currents, it still falls short of capturing what observations indicate. This may be due to the fact that even high-resolution models struggle to resolve certain smaller-scale processes—such as submesoscale activity, convection and atmospheric forcing—that serve as ‘seeding’ mechanisms for mesoscale activity through an inverse energy cascade (Sasaki et al., 2014; Callies and Ferrari, 2017; McWilliams, 2016; Brannigan et al., 2017).

Interestingly, even though in the EKE regional assessment WBC showed the largest differences between models and observations, eddy occurrence in the region is very well captured in the high-resolution models (Figure 12 (b)). We propose that this is likely due to the WBC regions having a lot of mesoscale features that are associated with eddies “pinching off” from the main current. These mesoscale features evolve in lifetimes less than 30 days and therefore are captured in the EKE fields. A further discussion on EBC system deficiencies is in the following subchapter on eddy birth.

There is a very high eddy occurrence in the North Atlantic region, especially around the Irminger Sea, and regions relevant to deep water formation. HADGEM3 MM does not capture this North Atlantic eddy peak. In ICON especially, the high occurrence region stretches further into the Norwegian Sea than in other datasets. This is likely linked to the sea-ice extent, as it has been shown to dampen eddies (Meneghello et al. 2021), and ICON shows a little sea-ice in this region when compared to other models (Figure 27 in D6.1 and section 3.2.1 in this report).

The median eddy occurrence in this region in ICON and AVISO show 30% higher occurrence and about 60% more eddy occurrences than in the medium resolution model.

A further analysis on eddy occurrence, separated by polarity of the eddies, revealed only small differences between cyclonic and anticyclonic eddies.

3.4 Birth and death frequency

Figure 13. Maps of the mean eddy birth frequency. The mean number of eddy births occurring in a 3 degree box per year for (a) IFS-FESOM, (b) ICON, (c) HADGEM3 HH, (d) HADGEM3 MM, (e) AVISO. The mean is calculated for the whole analysis period for eddies with a lifetime of at least 10 days.

Figure 14. Maps of the difference between mean eddy birth and death frequency for long-lived eddies. The difference between the mean number of eddy births occurring in a 3 degree box per year and the mean number of eddy deaths occurring in a 3 degree box per year for (a) IFS-FESOM, (b) ICON, (c) HADGEM3 HH, (d) HADGEM3 MM, (e) AVISO. Only long-lived (lifetime > 30 days) cyclonic and anticyclonic eddies are considered to reduce noise. The mean is calculated for the whole analysis period.

Figure 15. Eddy birth zonal mean. Zonal mean of the annual number of cyclonic and anticyclonic eddy births in 3 degree latitudinal bands for all models and observations. The mean is calculated for the whole analysis period for eddies with a lifetime of at least 10 days.

Figure 16. Regional eddy birth frequency distributions. Same as Figure 12 but for an eddy birth rate per year.

Very closely linked to eddy occurrence is eddy genesis or birth, which refers to the first time a tracked eddy is identified. While eddy birth and occurrence frequency are closely related, eddy birth frequency is not impacted by eddy lifetime, while eddy occurrence frequency is. Figure 13 shows eddy genesis per year binned in 3 degree boxes.

In general, the maps of eddy birth frequency capture the expected pattern, whereby eddy birth rate is higher around intense currents like the WBCs and the ACC and low in the ocean interior. Interestingly, eddy birth frequency in the MM model has little dependency on latitude. This means that eddies can be produced in almost all latitudes, but not at the right quantities and it only vaguely follows the expected pattern of more eddy birth in the vicinity of strong currents. The genesis rate and size of the eddy populations are better represented in high resolution models. Moreton et al. (2020) speculate that this improvement is likely the result of a better representation of the mean state in the higher-resolution models, especially in eddy-energetic regions. Additionally, the higher-resolution models are able to better generate eddy hot spots, which could partly be attributed to the improved representation of topography, which serves as a source of shear to form eddies (Deremble et al., 2016). Between high-resolution models and observations the same latitudinal birth frequency pattern is observed, whereby (without considering the poles) eddy birth is the lowest in low latitudes and steadily increases and peaks at about 60 degrees N and S.

Interestingly, eddy birth frequency in the models agrees less with the observations than eddy occurrence. The differences in zonal average suggest latitudes where AVISO dataset has biases in eddies with shorter lifetimes or model eddies have a higher survival rate, as discussed earlier. Figure 15 shows that only the area 10 degrees around equator likely agrees in eddy lifetime, as the occurrence and birth rates between models and observations are similar. However, in this area there are usually only few and short lived eddies due to very low values of Coriolis force (seen in Figure 7).

While both baroclinic and barotropic instabilities can generate mesoscale eddies in both WBCs and EBCs, baroclinic instability is more dominant in the energetic and vertically stratified environments of WBCs, whereas EBCs experience eddy generation through a combination of both instabilities, modulated by topography, wind forcing, and the presence of density fronts (Marchesiello et al., 2003; Combes et al., 2013). For example, in the Benguela Current system, mesoscale eddies are strongly influenced by coastal upwelling and interactions with bottom topography, where barotropic instability contributes to vortex stretching and eddy formation (Lutjeharms & Stockton, 1987). It is likely that some of the necessary sub-mesoscale processes are not resolved, leading to a lower eddy birth and occurrence. This is in agreement with Moreton et al. (2020) findings where they concluded that one of the main deficiencies is the low eddy population in subtropical gyre interiors, which reflects model biases at the Eastern Boundary Upwelling Systems and at the Indonesian outflow, where most of these eddies are generated in observations, while the WBC are well represented in eddy numbers and birth rates. Eddies

generated in Eastern Boundary Currents are important for transferring heat and nutrients into the nutrient-poor open ocean (Frenger et al., 2018; Gaube et al., 2014).

When the lifetime histogram of eddies (Figure 8) and the separation of short and long-lived eddies in Figure 14 is assessed, it is clear that around 60% of eddies in all datasets have a lifetime of only 10-30 days. These short-lived eddies don't travel great distances in their lifetime and very likely are born and die in the same vicinity. For this reason, to assess the difference between eddy birth and death places we chose to focus on longer-lived (lifetime >30 days) eddies, as birth and death locations should differ. For long-lived eddies in models and observations there is a clear pattern of eddy birth belts on the eastern sides of the basin and death places on the western edges of the basin. This is in agreement with eddies generally propagating east to west, with some exceptions. An agreement between birth and death places of models and the observations indicates that the long-lived eddy trajectories are representative of the observations. The medium resolution model is also able to capture this pattern.

3.5 Amplitude

Figure 17. Maps of absolute mean eddy amplitude. The mean absolute amplitude of cyclonic and anticyclonic eddy instances binned in 1 degree boxes for (a) IFS-FESOM, (b) ICON, (c) HADGEM3 HH, (d) HADGEM3 MM, (e) AVISO. The mean is calculated for the whole analysis period for eddies with a lifetime of at least 10 days.

Figure 18. Amplitude zonal mean. Zonal mean of the absolute eddy amplitude for cyclonic and anticyclonic eddies in 1 degree latitudinal bands for each of the models and observations. The mean is calculated for the whole analysis period for eddies with a lifetime of at least 10 days.

Figure 19. Regional amplitude distributions. Density distribution of the absolute eddy amplitude for cyclonic and anticyclonic eddies in 5 different ocean regions ((a) Eastern boundary currents, (b) Western boundary currents, (c) Equator, (d) Southern Ocean, (e) North Atlantic, see Figure 3) for all models and observations. The whole analysis period is considered for eddies with a lifetime of at least 10 days.

Eddy amplitude is the absolute difference between the maximum (for anticyclones) or minimum (cyclones) SSH within the eddy and the SSH value of the outermost closed SSH contour. Different signs for cyclonic and anticyclonic eddies is the reason we use absolute amplitude in this report.

Overall, eddy amplitude patterns in all models are well captured when compared to observations. In particular, it is noteworthy that both the areas of high eddy amplitude, like WBC and the ACC, and the areas of low-amplitude eddies, like the middle of gyres, are captured in the models. Globally and in each of the Figure 19 regions separately, observations show higher median amplitude (2.72 cm) than any of the models (ICON 2.14 cm, IFS-FESOM 1.71 cm, HADGEM3 HH 2.4 cm, HADGEM3 MM 1.57 cm), with ICON comparing the best (23% smaller than observations). Of the high-resolution models, IFS-FESOM shows the largest differences from observations with regional differences being largest in WBC region where median amplitude is 45% smaller of the observations. The best agreement between all datasets is at the equator (no more than 15 % lower amplitudes in model) and the largest differences in the WBC systems (up to 50% lower amplitudes in models).

In models, both eddy polarities exhibit the same pattern, with eddy amplitudes peaking in the strong western boundary currents and ACC; however, the amplitudes are approximately 20% higher for cyclonic eddies in these areas, when compared to anticyclonic eddies. In the rest of the ocean, eddy amplitudes are comparable for both polarities. Furthermore, there is a hemispheric contrast in eddy amplitude and with high-amplitude (amplitude > 10 cm) eddies in the Southern Hemisphere are more likely to be cyclonic, likely due to the gradient wind effect, which enhances cyclonic low-pressure centers, while weakening anticyclonic high-pressure centers. However, this mechanism does not explain the slight preference for anticyclones across most amplitudes and speeds in the Northern Hemisphere (Chelton et al., 2011).

The lower resolution HADGEM3 MM is comparable in eddy amplitude to the higher-resolution models (only 8% lower median amplitude than IFS-FESOM) with the biggest differences in the northern WBC regions where it does not capture the strong amplitude peak with approximately 40-50% lower peak than the rest of the datasets.

The lower amplitudes in models are somewhat expected, as smaller eddies are captured. Indeed, Amores et al. (2018) suggests that eddies identified on AVISO satellite altimetry have overestimated amplitudes and sizes due to bias in capturing only larger and "stronger" eddies.

3.6 Radius

Figure 20. Maps of mean eddy radius. Same as Figure 17 but for mean eddy radius (the radius of maximum geostrophic speed).

Figure 21. Radius zonal mean. Same as Figure 18 but for but for mean eddy radius (the radius of maximum geostrophic speed). Black line shows the theoretical Rossby radius of deformation computed with the climatological stratification from the IFS-FESOM.

Figure 22. Regional radius distributions. Same as Figure 19 but for mean eddy radius (the radius of maximum geostrophic speed) for the five regions shown in Figure 3.

The speed-radius is defined as the radius of a circle with the same area as the area of an eddy contour drawn on the maximum averaged geostrophic velocity. Overall, eddy radii follow the same pattern in observations and models, whereby the eddy size increases toward the lower latitudes. This pattern is expected, as the size of eddies tends to scale with the Rossby radius of deformation outside of the tropics (Theiss et al. 2004). In both observations and models, the eddies tend to be smaller than the theoretical Rossby radius in the tropics and larger in the extra-tropics, reflecting the multitude of processes that control eddy size, such as formation mechanisms, ocean-atmosphere interactions, and eddy life-history. This pattern is consistent with previous studies, such as Moreton et al. (2020) (their Figure 10), and reflects broader controls discussed in their section 3.4, including stratification, vertical structure, and surface forcing. In particular, at the equator, both models and observations show particularly small eddies compared to the local Rossby radius (Figure 21), a situation where the assumption of geostrophy breaks down due to the very weak Coriolis force. Additionally, theoretical work by Tulloch et al. (2011) suggests that the scale of maximum baroclinic instability depends systematically on latitude, further contributing to the observed deviations from the simple scaling with the Rossby radius across the global ocean.

Eddy size distribution in both polarities is comparable and follows the above-described patterns. In general, anticyclonic eddies tend to be slightly larger, as they are usually more stable and longer-lived (Chelton et al. 2011). The largest differences between polarities occur in the equatorial belt, where the cyclonic eddies are approximately 15% (20km) smaller in radius, compared to the anticyclonic eddies. However, these differences are visible only in models, not in observations.

The coarser resolution HADGEM3 MM model shows overall approximately 20% larger median radius than the high-resolution models and observations. This is the case in all latitudinal bands and regions (Figure 21). The Southern Ocean, the EBC and the equatorial regions all show the largest differences between the medium-resolution model and all other datasets, with approximately 25% larger median eddies in all cases in the HADGEM3 MM. Moreton et al. (2020) found the largest discrepancies between observations, medium- and high-resolution models in their radii (median radius 48 km, 14 km, 32 km, respectively). We don't find these stark differences in the current analysis, likely because they considered only eddies that live for more than a month, while we consider all eddies with lifetimes longer than 10 days. This means that we included about 50% more tracked eddies. The difference between our results and those of Morton et al. (2020) show the challenges associated with the comparison of eddy characteristics between studies with different eddy selection criteria.

An unexpected and consistent finding across all high-resolution models are streaks of smaller eddy sizes on both sides of equator in the tropical belt. The reason for this is still unknown.

4 Eddies and the sea ice

4.1 Eddies in the polar oceans: General overview

Observing mesoscale ocean eddies in the polar oceans, especially in the sea ice covered regions have remained a great challenge. Satellite and in-situ observation of eddies under sea ice is mainly limited by the presence of large ice floes. Also, due to decreasing Rossby Radius at these high latitudes, most global circulation models are too coarse to resolve the ocean mesoscale (Appen et al., 2022, Beech et al., 2025). With the EERIE models, we are able to overcome some of these challenges (Li et al., 2024, Beech et al., 2025). EERIE models are eddy rich and eddy permitting at these high latitudes where sea ice is present, which is found to be sufficient for reproducing dominant processes and key features. For example, Regan et al, (2020) used a high-resolution ($1/12^\circ$) model to simulate realistic features in the Beaufort Gyre in the Arctic. However, when approaching the poles, the resolution of the models is still limited in resolving eddies in some of the challenging regions, such as the shallow shelf regions (Nurser & Bacon, 2013, Müller et al., 2024). For the Southern Ocean, a daily sea level anomaly product covering the sea ice covered regions was created by Auger et al. (2021). Further, Auger et al (2023) investigated statistical properties of surface currents as well as coherent mesoscale eddies in the seasonally ice-covered Southern Ocean. We compare our results for the Southern Ocean against those by Auger et al. (2023), but to the best of our knowledge, no similar studies are present for the Arctic Ocean for comparison.

4.1.1 Eddy Amplitude

As a first step in our evaluation, we come back on some of the key eddy properties discussed in section 3 but with a focus on the polar oceans. Comparing the eddy amplitude from EERIE models against observations at mid and high latitudes (Figure 23), dominant features are the high amplitude eddies in the Gulf Stream and Kuroshio Current regions and their extensions, surrounding the Arctic, as well as the Antarctic Circumpolar Current (ACC). As already discussed in section 3.1, the agreement is strongest between HadGEM3-HH and AVISO for Gulf Stream, while the lower resolution model (HadGEM3-MM) underestimates the eddy amplitude. This is also valid for the Gulf Stream extension into the Norwegian Sea that is better reproduced in the high resolution EERIE models, compared to the medium resolution model. In ICON and IFS-FESOM eddy amplitude at the core of the Gulf Stream is slightly lower, and the current with higher eddy amplitude is spread in a wider area.

Figure 23. Maps of absolute mean eddy amplitude. The mean absolute amplitude of cyclonic and anticyclonic eddy instances binned in 1 degree boxes. The mean is calculated for the whole analysis period for eddies with a lifetime of at least 10 days. The summer and winter sea ice extent for the respective model and observation are shown using blue and red contours.

In the Southern Ocean, high eddy amplitude regions (east of Kerguelen Plateau (~60E), SouthEast Indian Ridge (~90 to 130E), Antarctic Pacific Ridge (~180-240E), and Scotia Arc (~300E) generated by interactions between the flow and the topography (Sallée et al. 2011, Yung et al., 2022) are captured in all models. The eddy amplitude in eddy hotspots in the ACC as well as in the western boundary currents are higher in the HadGEM3 HH and MM models, while its slightly lower in IFS-FESOM compared to the observations. Eddy amplitude under sea ice in both poles are substantially lower than in the open ocean. Lower amplitude at surface is expected, as sea ice exerts friction on the eddies below dampening and dissipating them (Meneghello et al 2020), decreasing the chance of developing high amplitude eddies.

4.1.2 Eddy Radius

Outside the sea ice zone, mean eddy radius in the high resolution EERIE models are generally similar to observations (Figure 24), while comparing the larger eddy occurrence, especially in the ACC band and Gulf Stream, they are a little larger in the models compared to observations. EERIE models (except IFS-FESOM) also seem to overestimate eddy radius in the North Pacific region. The HadGEM3-MM model overestimates eddy radius quite heavily and indicates possible issues in the eddy generation and/or detection in the coarse resolution, this is especially the case for large eddy radius detected close to the pole in the Arctic Ocean (also see section 3.1.6). Coarser resolution prevents simulating eddies with small radii, as it can only resolve features larger than the grid spacing (~25 km), hence it can only capture larger eddies (and is likely unrealistic for central Arctic). HadGEM3-HH also produces eddies with large radius close to the pole. In the sea ice zone, high resolution EERIE models tend to have lower mean eddy radius than observation. We hypothesise that observations may be biased towards detecting eddies of higher radius and relatively higher amplitude due to the challenges in identifying them in the high latitudes, while high resolution models can generate many smaller (radius) eddies, that are tracked and is then reflected in the mean eddy radius in this region.

Figure 24. Maps of mean eddy radius. Same as Figure 23 but for mean eddy radius (the radius of maximum geostrophic speed).

4.1.3 Eddy Birth and Death Frequency

Eddy birth (Figure 25) and death frequency (Figure 26) in the EERIE models are generally lower than that in AVISO, especially in the open ocean regions away from the coast and in strong currents. As discussed above, this may be due to the noise and uncertainties in the observations. However, compared to the high resolution EERIE models, HadGEM3-MM has much smaller eddy birth and death rates. Also, while eddy birth and death frequency are lower in the EERIE models, they still generate eddies in the same regions of high eddy birth/death frequency as in the observations. Improved topography may be helping capture the eddy hotspots in the high resolution models. In the northern hemisphere high eddy birth rates are seen south of Greenland and in the Norwegian Sea. This is captured well in the high resolution EERIE models but not in HadGEM3-MM. Considering the sea ice zone, we see very high eddy birth and death rates along the ice edge (red contour) in both hemispheres in AVISO but more systematically in the Southern Ocean., This is less pronounced in the EERIE models. This disparity is very likely arising from the limitation of detecting eddies under sea ice. AVISO cannot detect well eddies under sea ice, therefore, it consider ice-edge as region of eddy birth/death (as eddies move in and out of sea ice cover), while models don't encounter this issue and hence the eddy birth and death are more aligned with topography driven eddy hotspots.

Figure 25. Maps of the mean eddy birth frequency. The mean number of eddy births occurring in a 3 degree box per year for eddies with a lifetime of at least 10 days.

Figure 26. Maps of the mean eddy death frequency. Same as Figure 25, but for mean eddy death frequency.

4.2 Seasonal cycle of the eddies under Arctic sea ice

Polar oceans undergo strong seasonal variations, largely tied to the seasonal freeze and melt of sea ice. The characteristics of the upper ocean, as well as the interactions between the eddies and sea ice are expected to be different in the sea ice freezing period (autumn, winter) versus the melting period (spring, summer). Furthermore, winter expansion of sea ice cover allows for more occurrence of eddies under sea ice, while in summer, a very limited area is covered by ice and, therefore, the number of eddies under sea ice is also very low. Beyond this direct link, where the presence or absence of sea ice cover dictate whether there are eddies under sea ice and the size of the available sampling of eddies, the expansion and contraction of sea ice cover also change the mean characteristics in the ice cover regions.

In winter, the ice-covered zone around Antarctica expands equatorward into deeper oceanic regions, while in summer only the highest latitudes closer to the continent in shallow shelf regions remain ice covered. While in the Arctic, sea ice expands out of the shallow Arctic basin in summer into the North Pacific and North Atlantic Ocean regions. We thus expect that the properties of the under ice eddies will follow those geographical changes, with for instance on average smaller eddies in summer than in winter. It is therefore of importance to differentiate the seasonal changes in the eddy-ice-ocean dynamics. Here we present the statistics of eddies under sea ice in both poles as a first order quantitative assessment to evaluate whether the EERIE models simulate eddies in these high latitudes and if we have enough eddies to proceed to further specific analyses.

In figure 27, we check how the EERIE models compare in simulating eddies under Arctic sea ice and their general characteristics. We follow how the eddy characteristics change with the annual cycle of sea ice. The eddy count and total area of under ice eddies, all show the seasonal rise and fall concurrent with the sea ice growth and melt. The ICON model produces a higher number of eddies that have smaller radius. ICON also has a low Arctic sea ice area in summer (see contours in Figure 26) and subsequently very low eddy count and area of under ice eddies in summer. The HadGEM3 models have a lower eddy occurrence under sea ice, with lowest in the HadGEM3-MM model, which is less than half of that in ICON and IFS-FESOM in most periods (except summer, where eddy count drops in all models). There is no consistent signal amongst the models in producing more cyclonic or anticyclonic eddies: ICON and HadGEM3-HH produces more cyclonic eddies in general, while IFS-FESOM and HadGEM3-MM slight majority of anticyclonic eddies over cyclonic eddies. Focusing on the eddies in the marginal ice zone (MIZ), as expected, their relative input increases in the sea ice melting period, as most of the ice cover melts. In the MIZ, there is a majority for cyclonic eddies throughout the year.

Eddy characteristics under Arctic sea ice

Figure 27. Characteristics of eddies under Arctic sea ice for EERIE models and their seasonal evolution. Eddies under a minimum of 10% sea ice concentration. Climatology created from five years of daily eddy tracks and sea ice concentration for respective models. Evolution of the total sea ice area for models and observations (a). Total number of cyclonic and anticyclonic eddies under sea ice (b), total area of eddies under sea ice (c) their amplitude (d). Ratio of number of eddies in the marginal ice zones (mizN and mizS)

with total number of eddies under ice(e), and eddy radius (f). Period of low confidence in summer when the eddy numbers are low is shaded in grey.

The HadGEM3 models produce eddies of higher amplitude (especially in winter), while IFS-FESOM have low amplitude (especially for cyclonic eddies) through most of the year. Although seasonal changes in the eddy amplitude (higher in winter and lower in summer) is present in all models, this variability is more prominent in the IFS-FESOM and HadGEM3-HH models, primarily in the marginal ice zones (see Figure 28). The mean radius of the eddies does not display a clear and robust seasonal cycle between the models, the main difference between them being the larger eddies in HadGEM3-MM because of the coarser resolution (Figure 27).

Figure 28. Seasonal evolution of eddy amplitude under the three sea ice categories for EERIE models in the Arctic.

We further differentiate the statistics of eddies under sea ice based on the sea ice concentration (SIC) categories. The main motivation for this differentiation is based on observational and model studies that have shown that eddy property and distribution varied under various sea ice concentration ranges (Auger et al 2023, Manucharyan & Thompson 2022). Eddy

activity observed from satellites and ice-tethered moorings in the Arctic have shown that the friction exerted by the sea ice dissipates eddies, and prevents the formation of new ones under pack ice (Meneghello et al 2020). They found that there was a marked seasonal cycle close to the ocean surface with strong eddy activity during summer, followed by quiet winters, while subsurface eddies persisted all year long. Manucharyan & Thompson (2022) have demonstrated how sea ice eddy interaction can vary based on sea ice concentration or thickness. They found that, while high concentration pack ice exerts a dampening effect on the eddies, beyond a critical threshold, the low concentration sea ice exhibits tracer-like behavior, when the ice floes are smaller than the eddy. When sea ice acts like a tracer, especially in the MIZ, energized eddies enhance heat exchange between the subsurface ocean and the sea ice, accelerating its melt and constituting a positive feedback. Whereas, when sea ice concentration is high and the ice floe is relatively stationary, the frictional forces between the eddy and sea ice gives rise to Ekman induced vertical motions termed 'Eddy Ice Pumping' (EIP) producing a net upward vertical heat flux warming the core of anticyclonic eddies, reducing sea ice thickness, and re-stratifying the water column from resulting sea ice melt (Gupta et al 2020).

Eddy Radius under Arctic sea ice (km)

Figure 29. Seasonal evolution of eddy radius under the three sea ice categories for EERIE models. Note that the y-axis range for HadGEM3-MM is higher than the other models in the Arctic.

We use ice categories similar to that used in Auger et al 2023, : marginal ice zone North ('miz-N'; SIC 10 to 40%), marginal ice zone South ('miz-S'; SIC 40 to 70%), and ice pack ('ice'; SIC more than 70%). When we differentiate the eddies under various sea ice concentration ranges, we find that in the Arctic, eddies under the ice pack (SIC>70%) dominate in all EERIE models through most of the year. The mean characteristics of the eddies (Figure 27) are thus similar to the one observed in the ice pack (Figures 28-29). The seasonal cycle of the eddy amplitude in all the ice categories follows the one of the ice pack. Additionally, the amplitude of the eddies is higher in the marginal ice zone than under pack ice, corresponding well to the theoretical arguments developed above. The differences between miz-N and miz-S are less systematic, maybe because of a threshold effect or because of additional factors, such as the geographical distribution of the two regions, but identifying them clearer would require further analyses.

On evaluating the evolution of eddy radius under the sea ice categories, a signal of increasing radii in summer is found in all models (Figure 29). Due to the limited number of eddy

occurrences under summer ice cover, we have low confidence, yet this signal seems to be consistent in all models. This is likely due to the changes in the geographic settings for Arctic sea ice, moving from winter to summer. In winter, Arctic sea ice extends into the shallow shelf regions populated by eddies of smaller radii, but as the ice cover shrinks, sea ice cover is located mostly in the central Arctic Ocean, with deeper water column and eddies of larger radii. It is also likely that as the sea ice disintegrates into smaller floes in summer, the frictional force acting on eddies to dissipate them is weaker allowing for larger eddies to exist.

4.3 Eddies under Antarctic sea ice

In the Antarctic, the effect of the seasonal sea ice cycle is clear and evident in all parameters (Figure 30). Notably the eddy amplitude and radius follow the sea ice expansion and melt. Sea ice expansion in the Antarctic implies sea ice cover moving from high latitude and shallow shelf regions into lower latitudes as well as deeper open ocean. This is consistent with the larger eddies in winter, and leads thus to a clearer signal than for the Arctic. In winter, except IFS-FESOM, all other EERIE models underestimate the sea ice cover, especially in the Pacific sector. This reduced winter ice cover has clear consequences in the eddy count for the different models: IFS-FESOM simulates a higher number of eddies, followed by ICON, and similar to the Arctic, HadGEM3 models simulate lower number of eddies under sea ice. As in the case of the Arctic, (also in Figure 24), the eddy radius simulated by HadGEM3-MM is considerably higher than the other EERIE models. It is interesting to note that all the high resolution EERIE models converge in the mean eddy radius in winter, and to a good extent they also converge in mean eddy amplitude in winter.

Under the different sea ice categories, eddy amplitudes in the miz-N and miz-S categories peak around September (when the sea ice extent is maximum). This is clear in IFS-FESOM, and the HadGEM3 models, and is very likely the result of sea ice cover expanding into the region of high amplitude eddies closer to the ACC. There are only small changes in the amplitude of eddies under the pack ice throughout the year, except a small reduction around June/July in IFS-FESOM, HadGEM3-HH, and ICON. The cause of this dip is not clear, but it is likely the dampening effect of sea ice as it starts to form more consolidated pack ice. The mean amplitude can be variable in summer but this is based on a very small number of eddies and thus not meaningful.

Eddy characteristics under Antarctic sea ice

Figure 30. Characteristics of eddies under Antarctic sea ice for EERIE models and their seasonal evolution. Eddies under a minimum of 10% sea ice concentration. Climatology created from five years of daily eddy tracks and sea ice concentration for respective models. Evolution of the total sea ice area for models and observations (a). Total number of cyclonic and anticyclonic eddies under sea ice (b), total area of eddies under sea ice (c) their amplitude (d). Ratio of number of eddies in the marginal ice zones (mizN and mizS)

with total number of eddies under ice(e), and eddy radius (f). Period of low confidence in summer when the eddy numbers are low is shaded in grey.

Eddy Amplitude under Antarctic sea ice

Figure 31. Seasonal evolution of eddy amplitude under the three sea ice categories for EERIE models in the Antarctic.

Eddy Radius under Arctic sea ice

Figure 32. Seasonal evolution of eddy radius under the three sea ice categories for EERIE models. Note that the y-axis range for HadGEM3-MM is higher than the other models in the Antarctic.

Unlike the Arctic, the mean radius of eddies under the Antarctic sea ice show a seasonal pattern following the sea ice cycle (Figure 32). Interestingly in most cases the eddy radius among the different categories have less difference and in some cases the mean eddy radius range even converges in winter (IFS-FESOM). However, in most cases, the eddies under the ice pack have larger radii than in other ice categories. This is a surprising behaviour, as one would expect the eddies in the marginal ice zones, which are generally in lower latitudes and closer to the ACC to have larger radii, than those inside the ice pack. The reason for this behaviour is not known at present, but it would be interesting to assess it in future work.

In their investigation of statistical properties of mesoscale eddies in the Southern Ocean, Auger et al., (2023) found cyclonic eddies more abundant than anticyclonic eddies in regions with low sea ice concentration (marginal ice zone). In our analysis, we find consistently higher cyclonic eddies than anticyclonic eddies under the ice pack, while such a relation is less clear in the marginal ice zones. They also found that eddy amplitude is highest in low sea ice concentration regions (~3 cm) and lowest in high sea ice concentration regions (~2 cm). Our findings are consistent with their results, and also the amplitudes match in a similar range.

5 Discussion and Conclusion

5.1 Resolution-dependent fidelity of mesoscale eddies

The multi-model analysis presented in this report demonstrates that high-resolution ocean models (<10 km) achieve substantial improvements in representing mesoscale eddy characteristics compared to medium-resolution (~25 km) configurations. High-resolution EERIE models capture between 82-88% of observed eddies, while the medium-resolution HadGEM3-MM configuration represents only about 55% of them. This step-change in fidelity occurs specifically when transitioning from the eddy-permitting regime to the eddy-resolving (consequently eddy-rich) regime.

Our findings align with previous work by Moreton et al. (2020), who demonstrated that eddy-rich resolution (~1/12°) significantly improved the representation of eddy populations compared to eddy-permitting resolution (~1/4°). Their analysis showed a 60% increase in eddy numbers and 23% increase in eddy longevity when moving to higher resolution. The present multi-model comparison confirms these results while extending them across different model families (with independent numerical schemes, parameterisations, etc.), suggesting a robustness in these resolution-dependent improvements.

Examining specific eddy characteristics reveals consistent patterns in resolution-dependent improvements:

Population statistics: The medium-resolution model (HadGEM3-MM) captures only ~55% of observed eddy numbers globally, compared to 82-88% in high-resolution models. This improvement with resolution is particularly pronounced in climatically important regions such as the North Atlantic, where MM shows ~60% fewer eddies—an area critical for deep water formation and the closure of the Meridional Overturning Circulation.

Eddy structure: MM eddies are systematically larger (~20% larger median radius) across all latitudinal bands and regions compared to both observations and high-resolution models. This suggests that the inability to resolve finer features artificially inflates the size of the eddies..

Energetics: MM captures only ~45% of global eddy kinetic energy compared to observations, with particularly pronounced deficits in Western Boundary Currents. The high-resolution models in contrast capture ~75% of the observed eddy kinetic energy.

Spatio-temporal patterns: The birth frequency distribution in MM is more spatially uniform, lacking the expected concentration near intense currents that is captured by high-resolution models and evident in observations.

The multi-scale nature of oceanic dynamics requires a more nuanced assessment of resolution benefits across different regions. In subtropical and mid-latitude regions, further refinement from ~ 10 km to 5 km resolution (e.g., ICON model run) provides modest additional benefits, particularly in representing fine-scale structures and energetics. However, in polar regions, the tripolar grid of HadGEM3-HH achieves comparable resolution (~ 4 km in the Arctic) to ICON's globally uniform 5 km grid, with consequently similar ability to resolve high-latitude mesoscale features. We therefore see many of these gains are regional or partially masked instead by inter-model differences. Indeed, still the most substantial improvements in model fidelity occur during the transition from eddy-permitting ($1/4^\circ$, ~ 25 km) to eddy-resolving ($1/12^\circ$, ~ 9 km) resolution, particularly for western boundary currents like the Gulf Stream, with more modest gains thereafter (see e.g., review by Hewitt et al. 2017, and specifically McClean et al. 2011, Hewitt et al. 2016, Roberts et al. 2018, Roberts et al. 2020). Consequently, instead of models being systematically different from observations, these high-resolution EERIE models broadly converge within the constraints of observational uncertainty.

5.2 Regional biases in mesoscale representation

Despite the overall improvements in eddy representation at higher resolution, regional differences and biases now emerge more prominently across the models. These regional variations highlight fundamental challenges in accurately simulating the complex, non-linear, and coupled dynamics controlling eddy formation, propagation, and dissipation.

The amalgamated Western Boundary Current regions exhibit some notable biases, with high-resolution models capturing only about 60% of the observed EKE, despite accurately representing eddy occurrence frequency. This apparent paradox reflects the substantial heterogeneity in mesoscale motions, where coherent eddies constitute only a fraction of the total kinetic energy budget. Western boundary currents feature numerous non-eddy mesoscale features—including filaments, meanders, and frontal structures—that contribute to the EKE while remaining distinct from identifiable coherent vortices. Consequently, while the models here correctly simulate eddy populations, they appear to underestimate the energetic contributions from these auxiliary mesoscale features. The positional biases of Western Boundary Currents—particularly the Gulf Stream and Kuroshio—deviate from observations in most models, with the Kuroshio separating too far north and the Gulf Stream exhibiting an overly zonal orientation. These positional biases are consistent with findings from coupled model studies (Chassignet and Xu, 2017) and likely contribute to downstream biases in eddy characteristics.

Eastern Boundary Current regions represent a particular challenge, with high-resolution models showing approximately 15% lower median eddy occurrence than observations, and medium-resolution models exhibiting a 35% deficit. This is consistent with Moreton et al. (2020),

who identified the low eddy population in subtropical gyre interiors as reflecting model biases at Eastern Boundary Upwelling Systems. The failure to still adequately resolve submesoscale activity and convection that feed the inverse energy cascade likely contributes to these biases. Additionally, the models struggle to capture the propagation of long-lived eddies observed from coastal generation sites into the open ocean.

The Southern Ocean is another region with particularly important mesoscale dynamics. The mesoscale biases in the Southern Ocean are found to be a consequence of biases in the mean state. One particular outlier is IFS-FESOM, which contained ~25% lower EKE relative to both observations and the other models. This is nonetheless consistent with its proportionally weaker (also ~25%) Antarctic Circumpolar Current. This highlights the intricate connection between mean flow strength and eddy characteristics – particularly important for the Southern Ocean where eddy compensation and saturation mechanisms dictate the response to changing winds (Munday et al., 2013). Finally, the improved representation of topographic features in high-resolution models provides the eddy generation sites and supports eddy hotspots that remain under-resolved in medium-resolution simulations.

5.3 Cyclonic-anticyclonic eddy asymmetry

While our analysis primarily focuses on the combined eddy field rather than distinguishing between cyclonic and anticyclonic eddies, the models successfully reproduce observed asymmetries between these two populations. Consistent with observational evidence (Chelton et al., 2011) and established theory (Arai & Yamagata, 1994), anticyclonic eddies in the models tend to be slightly larger and longer-lived than their cyclonic counterparts. This asymmetry is pronounced in the equatorial region, where cyclonic eddies are ~15% smaller than anticyclonic eddies, although this difference appears more clearly in models than in observations. The models' ability to capture these subtle yet physically important differences between cyclonic and anticyclonic eddies suggests they correctly represent fundamental aspects of mesoscale eddy dynamics – including an enhanced stability of anticyclones to external strain (Graves et al., 2006), as well as preferential topographic and baroclinic generation (Perret et al., 2006, Perret et al., 2011).

5.4 Eddies in high latitudes and under sea ice

The representation of mesoscale eddies in polar regions presents distinct challenges due to the small Rossby radius of deformation and the additional mechanical damping effect of sea ice. Notably, the models capture the theoretical expectation of amplitude attenuation under pack ice due to frictional dissipation, with systematically lower eddy amplitudes observed under high

sea ice concentration compared to marginal ice zones. The seasonal modulation of eddy characteristics – showing winter-summer contrasts in both amplitude and radius – further demonstrates the models' ability to represent complex ice-ocean coupling processes, including the eddy-ice pumping mechanism described in recent literature (Manucharyan & Thompson, 2022).

Significant uncertainties still remain in evaluating eddy characteristics in ice-covered regions. The fundamental limitations of observational products – particularly the inability of satellite altimetry to detect eddies under sea ice – create artificial discontinuities at the ice edge, manifesting as anomalously high birth/death rates in AVISO data that are not replicated in the models. Additionally, inter-model differences in sea ice distribution affect the sampling domain of under-ice eddies, complicating direct comparisons. These challenges in validating polar eddy dynamics, along with the critical role these eddies play in Antarctic and Arctic climate, motivate the dedicated analysis to be made in deliverable 5.4 focused specifically on eddies in polar regions.

5.5 Conclusion

This multi-model assessment demonstrates that eddy-resolving coupled climate models accurately capture fundamental mesoscale ocean dynamics. The consistency of various eddy statistics across independent model architectures provides validation of their physical fidelity. This agreement broadly extends across multiple higher-order metrics including population statistics, structural properties, and energetics, establishing confidence in the EERIE models' representation of mesoscale processes.

Despite regional biases in Eastern Boundary Current systems and Western Boundary Current energetics, these simulations reproduce essential physical characteristics of mesoscale eddies with sufficient accuracy to address a number of important scientific questions:

1. Eddy saturation mechanism modulating the Southern Ocean response to wind forcing
2. Mesoscale ocean-atmosphere interactions affecting momentum, heat, & carbon fluxes
3. Eddy-driven transport & circulation and its contribution to global budgets
4. Coherent eddy lifecycle dynamics to diagnose and improve parameterisation schemes
5. Mesoscale–submesoscale interactions as revealed by new observational platforms (SWOT) and EERIE model synthesis

Further work within the EERIE project will leverage these high-resolution simulations to quantify how mesoscale dynamics may evolve under changing climate conditions, thereby improving projections of regional and global climate.

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